

Some new equilibrium existence theorems for pair of abstract economies

A.K.Dubey¹, Rita Shukla², R.P.Dubey³

¹Department of Mathematics, Bhilai Institute of Technology,
Bhilai House, Durg, Chhattisgarh 491001, India

² Department of Mathematics, Shri Shankracharya College of Engineering
and Technology, Bhilai, Chhattisgarh 490020, India

³Department of Mathematics, Dr. C.V.Raman University,
Bilaspur, Chhattisgarh 495113, India

Corresponding author e-mail:anilkumardby70@gmail.com

Abstract.

In this paper, we prove some new common equilibrium existence theorems for pair of non-compact abstract economies with an uncountable number of agents.

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1. Introduction and Preliminaries

The existence of equilibria in an abstract economy with compact strategy sets in \mathbb{R}^n was proved by G. Debreu [3]. Since then many generalizations of Debreu's theorem appeared in many directions (see [4],[5],[12],[13],[14],[15],[16],[17],[18], and the references therein).

The purpose of this paper is to give some new common equilibrium existence theorems for pair of non-compact abstract economies with an uncountable number of agents with an general constraint correspondences and preference correspondences. Our results improve and generalize some known results in literature[4,11,16,18].

Now we give some notations and definitions that are needed in the sequel.

Let A be a subset of a topological space. We shall denote by 2^A and \bar{A} the family of all subsets of A and the closure of A in X , respectively. If A is a subset of a topological vector space X , we shall denote by coA and $\bar{co}A$ the convex hull of A and the closed convex hull of A , respectively.

Let X, Y be two topological spaces and $T: X \rightarrow 2^Y$ be a multivalued mapping. T is said to be upper semicontinuous (respectively, almost upper semicontinuous) if for any $x \in X$ and any open set V in Y with $T(x) \subset V$, there exists an open neighborhood U of x in X such that $T(z) \subset V$ (respectively, $T(z) \subset \bar{V}$) for $z \in U$. Obviously, an upper semicontinuous multi-valued mapping is almost upper semicontinuous (see [12],[16]). T is said to be lower semicontinuous if for any open set V in Y , the set $\{x \in X: T(x) \cap V \neq \emptyset\}$ is open in X . It is clear that T is upper semicontinuous (respectively, lower semicontinuous), if and only if for

any open set (respectively, closed set) M in Y , the set $\{x \in X: T(x) \subset M\}$ is open (respectively, closed) in X . T is said to have open graph in $X \times Y$ if the set $\{(x, y): x \in X, y \in T(x)\}$ is open in $X \times Y$.

An abstract and socio-economy are a family of quadruples $\Gamma_1 = (X_i; A_i, B_i; P_{2i+1})_{i \in I}$ and $\Gamma_2 = (X_i; A_i, B_i; P_{2i+2})_{i \in I}$ respectively, where I is a finite or an infinite set of agents, X_i is a nonempty topological space (a choice set), $A_i, B_i: X = \prod_{j \in I} X_j \rightarrow 2^{X_i}$ are constraint correspondences and $P_{2i+1}, P_{2i+2}: X \rightarrow 2^{X_i}$ are preference correspondences. A common equilibrium of Γ_1 and Γ_2 is a point $\hat{x} \in X$, such that for each $i \in I, \hat{x}_i \in \overline{B_i(\hat{x})}$ and $P_{2i+1}(\hat{x}) \cap A_i(\hat{x}) = \emptyset; P_{2i+2}(\hat{x}) \cap A_i(\hat{x}) = \emptyset$.

$\Gamma_1 = (X_i; P_{2i+1})_{i \in I}$ and $\Gamma_2 = (X_i; P_{2i+2})_{i \in I}$ are said to be a pair of qualitative game if for any $i \in I, X_i$ is a strategy set of player i , and $P_{2i+1}, P_{2i+2}: X = \prod_{j \in I} X_j \rightarrow 2^{X_i}$ are preference correspondences of player i . A common maximal element of Γ_1 and Γ_2 is a point $\hat{x} \in X$, such that $P_{2i+1}(\hat{x}) \cap P_{2i+2}(\hat{x}) = \emptyset$ for all $i \in I$.

Lemma 1.1.[11]

Let I be an index set. For each $i \in I$, let X_i be a nonempty convex subset of a Hausdorff locally convex topological vector space E_i, D_i a nonempty compact subset of X_i and $S_i, T_i: X = \prod_{K \in I} X_K \rightarrow 2^{D_i}$ are two multivalued mappings with the following conditions:

- (1) for any $x \in X, \emptyset \neq \overline{\partial} S_i(x) \subset T_i(x)$,
- (2) S_i is almost upper semicontinuous.

Then there exists a point $\hat{x} \in D = \prod_{K \in I} D_K$, such that $\hat{x}_i \in T_i(\hat{x})$ for all $i \in I$.

Lemma 1.2.[18]

Let I be an index set. For each $i \in I$, let X_i be a nonempty convex subset of a Hausdorff locally convex topological vector space E_i, D_i a nonempty compact metrizable subset of X_i and $S_i, T_i: X = \prod_{K \in I} X_K \rightarrow 2^{D_i}$ are two multivalued mappings with the following conditions:

- (1) for any $x \in X, \emptyset \neq \overline{\partial} S_i(x) \subset T_i(x)$,
- (2) S_i is lower semicontinuous.

Then there exists a point $\hat{x} \in D = \prod_{K \in I} D_K$, such that $\hat{x}_i \in T_i(\hat{x})$ for all $i \in I$.

2. Common Equilibrium Existence Theorems

In this section, we give some new common equilibrium existence theorems for pair of abstract economies.

Theorem 2.1. Let $\Gamma_1 = (X_i; A_i, B_i; P_{2i+1})_{i \in I}$ and $\Gamma_2 = (X_i; A_i, B_i; P_{2i+2})_{i \in I}$ be a pair of generalized games (abstract economy), where I be any index set such that for each $i \in I$:

- (1) X_i be a nonempty convex subset of a Hausdorff locally convex topological vector space E_i and D_i is a nonempty compact subset of X_i .
- (2) For all $x \in X = \prod_{i \in I} X_i, P_{2i+1}(x) \subset D_i$ and $P_{2i+2}(x) \subset D_i, A_i(x) \subset B_i(x) \subset D_i$, and $B_i(x)$ is nonempty convex.
- (3) The set $W_i = \{x \in X: A_i(x) \cap P_{2i+1}(x) \neq \emptyset \text{ and } A_i(x) \cap P_{2i+2}(x) \neq \emptyset\}$ is open in X .
- (4) The mappings $H_i, G_i: X \rightarrow 2^{D_i}$, defined by

$$H_i(x) = A_i(x) \cap P_{2i+1}(x)$$

and

$$G_i(x) = A_i(x) \cap P_{2i+2}(x), \forall x \in X$$

are upper semicontinuous and $B_i: X \rightarrow 2^{D_i}$ is upper semicontinuous.

- (5) For each $x \in W_i, x_i \notin \overline{\partial}(A_i(x) \cap P_{2i+1}(x))$ and also $x_i \notin \overline{\partial}(A_i(x) \cap P_{2i+2}(x))$.

Then Γ_1 and Γ_2 have a common equilibria point, i.e, there exists a point $\hat{x} \in D = \prod_{i \in I} D_i$, such that $\hat{x}_i \in \overline{B_i(\hat{x})}; P_{2i+1}(\hat{x}) \cap A_i(\hat{x}) = \emptyset$ and $P_{2i+2}(\hat{x}) \cap A_i(\hat{x}) = \emptyset$ for all $i \in I$.

Proof. For each $i \in I$ and $x \in X$, let

$$S_i(x) = \begin{cases} A_i(x) \cap P_{2i+1}(x), & \text{if } x \in W_i, \\ B_i(x), & \text{if } x \notin W_i, \end{cases}$$

and

$$T_i(x) = \begin{cases} \overline{CO}(A_i(x) \cap P_{2i+1}(x)), & \text{if } x \in W_i, \\ \overline{B_i(x)}, & \text{if } x \notin W_i. \end{cases}$$

Then, $S_i, T_i: X \rightarrow 2^{D_i}$ are two multivalued mappings with nonempty values and $\overline{CO}S_i(x) \subset T_i(x)$ for all $x \in X$.

Now, we prove that S_i is upper semicontinuous. In fact, for each open set V in D_i , the set

$$\begin{aligned} \{x \in X: S_i(x) \subset V\} &= \{x \in W_i: A_i(x) \cap P_{2i+1}(x) \subset V\} \cup \\ &\quad \{x \in X \setminus W_i: B_i(x) \subset V\} \\ &\subset \{x \in W_i: H_i(x) \subset V\} \cup \{x \in X: B_i(x) \subset V\}. \end{aligned}$$

On the other hand, when $x \in W_i$ and $H_i(x) \subset V$, we have $S_i(x) = H_i(x) \subset V$. When $x \in X$ and $B_i(x) \subset V$, since $H_i(x) \subset B_i(x)$, we know that $S_i(x) \subset V$ and so

$$\{x \in W_i: H_i(x) \subset V\} \cup \{x \in X: B_i(x) \subset V\} \subset \{x \in X: S_i(x) \subset V\}.$$

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} \{x \in X: S_i(x) \subset V\} &= \{x \in W_i: H_i(x) \subset V\} \cup \{x \in X: B_i(x) \subset V\} \\ &= W_i \cap \{x \in X: H_i(x) \subset V\} \cup \{x \in X: B_i(x) \subset V\}. \end{aligned}$$

Since H_i and B_i are upper semicontinuous, the sets $\{x \in X: H_i(x) \subset V\}$ and $\{x \in X: B_i(x) \subset V\}$ are open. It follows that $\{x \in X: S_i(x) \subset V\}$ is open and so the mapping $S_i: X \rightarrow 2^{D_i}$ is upper semicontinuous.

By Lemma 1.1, there exists a point $\hat{x} \in D = \prod_{i \in I} D_i$, such that, $\hat{x}_i \in T_i(\hat{x})$ for all $i \in I$. By Condition (5), we have $\hat{x}_i \in \overline{B_i(\hat{x})}$ and $P_{2i+1}(\hat{x}) \cap A_i(\hat{x}) = \emptyset$ for all $i \in I$.

Similarly, it can be established that for each $i \in I$, $\hat{x}_i \in \overline{B_i(\hat{x})}$ and $P_{2i+2}(\hat{x}) \cap A_i(\hat{x}) = \emptyset$, i.e., Γ_1 and Γ_2 have a common equilibria point. This completes the proof of Theorem.

Theorem 2.2. Let $\Gamma_1 = (X_i; A_i, B_i; P_{2i+1})_{i \in I}$ and $\Gamma_2 = (X_i; A_i, B_i; P_{2i+2})_{i \in I}$ be a pair of generalized games (abstract economy), such that for each $i \in I$, the following conditions are satisfied.

- (1) X_i is a nonempty convex subset of a Hausdorff locally convex topological vector space E_i and D_i is a nonempty compact metrizable subset of X_i .
- (2) For all $x \in X = \prod_{i \in I} X_i$, $P_{2i+1}(x) \subset D_i$ and $P_{2i+2}(x) \subset D_i$, $A_i(x) \subset B_i(x) \subset D_i$ and $B_i(x)$ is nonempty convex.
- (3) The set $W_i = \{x \in X: A_i(x) \cap P_{2i+1}(x) \neq \emptyset \text{ and } A_i(x) \cap P_{2i+2}(x) \neq \emptyset\}$ is closed in X .
- (4) The mappings $A_i: X \rightarrow 2^{D_i}$ (respectively, $P_{2i+1}, P_{2i+2}: X \rightarrow 2^{D_i}$) is lower semicontinuous, P_{2i+1}, P_{2i+2} (respectively, A_i) have open graph in $X \times D_i$, and $B_i: X \rightarrow 2^{D_i}$ is lower semicontinuous.
- (5) For each $x \in W_i$, $x_i \notin \overline{CO}(A_i(x) \cap P_{2i+1}(x))$ and also $x_i \notin \overline{CO}(A_i(x) \cap P_{2i+2}(x))$.

Then Γ_1 and Γ_2 have a common equilibria point, i.e, there exists a point $\hat{x} \in D = \prod_{i \in I} D_i$, such that $\hat{x}_i \in \overline{B_i(\hat{x})}; P_{2i+1}(\hat{x}) \cap A_i(\hat{x}) = \emptyset$ and $P_{2i+2}(\hat{x}) \cap A_i(\hat{x}) = \emptyset$ for all $i \in I$.

Proof. For each $i \in I$ and $x \in X$, let

$$S_i(x) = \begin{cases} A_i(x) \cap P_{2i+1}(x), & \text{if } x \in W_i, \\ B_i(x), & \text{if } x \notin W_i, \end{cases}$$

and

$$T_i(x) = \begin{cases} \overline{c\bar{o}}(A_i(x) \cap P_{2i+1}(x)), & \text{if } x \in W_i, \\ \overline{B_i(x)}, & \text{if } x \notin W_i. \end{cases}$$

Then, $S_i, T_i: X \rightarrow 2^{D_i}$ are two multivalued mappings with nonempty values and $\overline{c\bar{o}}S_i(x) \subset T_i(x)$ for all $x \in X$.

From Condition (4) and [19, Lemma 4.2], we know that the mapping $H_i: X \rightarrow 2^{D_i}$ defined by

$$H_i(x) = A_i(x) \cap P_{2i+1}(x), \forall x \in X$$

is lower semicontinuous.

Now, we prove that S_i is lower semicontinuous. In fact, for each closed set V in D_i , as in the proof of Theorem 2.1, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \{x \in X: S_i(x) \subset V\} &= \{x \in W_i: A_i(x) \cap P_{2i+1}(x) \subset V\} \cup \\ &\quad \{x \in X \setminus W_i: B_i(x) \subset V\} \\ &= \{x \in W_i: H_i(x) \subset V\} \cup \{x \in X: B_i(x) \subset V\} \\ &= W_i \cap \{x \in W_i: H_i(x) \subset V\} \cup \{x \in X: B_i(x) \subset V\}. \end{aligned}$$

Since H_i and B_i are lower semicontinuous, the sets $\{x \in X: H_i(x) \subset V\}$ and $\{x \in X: B_i(x) \subset V\}$ are closed. It follows that $\{x \in X: S_i(x) \subset V\}$ is closed and so the mapping $S_i: X \rightarrow 2^{D_i}$ is lower semicontinuous.

By Lemma 1.2, there exists a point $\hat{x} \in D = \prod_{i \in I} D_i$, such that, $\hat{x}_i \in T_i(\hat{x})$ for all $i \in I$. By Condition (5), we have $\hat{x}_i \in \overline{B_i(\hat{x})}$ and $P_{2i+1}(\hat{x}) \cap A_i(\hat{x}) = \emptyset$ for all $i \in I$.

Similarly, it can be established that for each $i \in I$, $\hat{x}_i \in \overline{B_i(\hat{x})}$ and $P_{2i+2}(\hat{x}) \cap A_i(\hat{x}) = \emptyset$, i.e., Γ_1 and Γ_2 have a common equilibria point. This completes the proof of Theorem.

Theorem 2.3. Let $\Gamma_1 = (X_i; A_i, B_i; P_{2i+1})_{i \in I}$ and $\Gamma_2 = (X_i; A_i, B_i; P_{2i+2})_{i \in I}$ be a pair of generalized games (abstract economy), such that for each $i \in I$, the following conditions are satisfied.

- (1) X_i be a nonempty convex subset of a Hausdorff locally convex topological vector space E_i and D_i is a nonempty compact subset of X_i .
- (2) For all $x \in X = \prod_{i \in I} X_i$, $P_{2i+1}(x) \subset D_i$ and $P_{2i+2}(x) \subset D_i$, $A_i(x) \subset B_i(x) \subset D_i$, $P_{2i+1}(x)$ and $P_{2i+2}(x)$ are convex and $B_i(x)$ is nonempty convex.
- (3) The set $W_i = \{x \in X: A_i(x) \cap P_{2i+1}(x) \neq \emptyset \text{ and } A_i(x) \cap P_{2i+2}(x) \neq \emptyset\}$ is open in X .
- (4) The mappings $B_i, P_{2i+1}, P_{2i+2}: X \rightarrow 2^{D_i}$ are almost upper semicontinuous.
- (5) For each $x \in W_i$, $x_i \notin \overline{B_i(x)} \cap \overline{P_{2i+1}(x)}$ and also $x_i \notin \overline{B_i(x)} \cap \overline{P_{2i+2}(x)}$.

Then Γ_1 and Γ_2 have a common equilibria point, i.e, there exists a point $\hat{x} \in D = \prod_{i \in I} D_i$, such that $\hat{x}_i \in \overline{B_i(\hat{x})}$; $P_{2i+1}(\hat{x}) \cap A_i(\hat{x}) = \emptyset$ and $P_{2i+2}(\hat{x}) \cap A_i(\hat{x}) = \emptyset$ for all $i \in I$.

Proof. For each $i \in I$ and $x \in X$, let

$$T_i(x) = \begin{cases} \overline{B_i(x)} \cap \overline{P_{2i+1}(x)}, & \text{if } x \in W_i, \\ \overline{B_i(x)}, & \text{if } x \notin W_i. \end{cases}$$

Then, $T_i: X \rightarrow 2^{D_i}$ is a multivalued mapping with nonempty closed convex values. Since B_i and P_{2i+1} are two almost upper semicontinuous multivalued mappings with convex values, by [12, Lemmas 1 and 2], we

know that \overline{B}_i and $\overline{P_{2i+1}}$ are upper semicontinuous. Hence, $\overline{B}_i \cap \overline{P_{2i+1}}$ is upper semicontinuous by [1, Proposition 3.1.7 and Theorem 3.1.8]. As in the proof the Theorem 2.1, we know that T_i is upper semicontinuous.

Define mapping $T: X \rightarrow 2^D$ by $T(x) = \prod_{i \in I} T_i(x), \forall x \in X$,

then T is an upper semicontinuous multivalued mapping with nonempty closed convex valued by [9, Lemma 3]. Therefore, by applying Himmelberg's fixed-point theorem [10], there exists a point $\hat{x} \in D = \prod_{i \in I} D_i$, such that, $\hat{x}_i \in T_i(\hat{x})$ for all $i \in I$. By Condition (5), we have $\hat{x}_i \in \overline{B}_i(\hat{x})$ and $P_{2i+1}(\hat{x}) \cap A_i(\hat{x}) = \emptyset$ for all $i \in I$.

Similarly, it can be established that for each $i \in I$, $\hat{x}_i \in \overline{B}_i(\hat{x})$ and $P_{2i+2}(\hat{x}) \cap A_i(\hat{x}) = \emptyset$, i.e., Γ_1 and Γ_2 have a common equilibria point. This completes the proof of Theorem.

Remark: In Theorem 2.1-2.3, when $A_i(x) = B_i(x) = X_i$ for all $x \in X$ and $i \in I$, we can obtain some new common existence theorems of maximal element for qualitative games.

References

- [1] J.P. Aubin and I. Ekeland, Applied Nonlinear Analysis, John Wiley and Sons, New York (1984).
- [2] S.S. Chang, X. Wu and Z.F. Shen, Economic equilibrium theorems of Shafer—Sonnenschein version and nonempty intersection theorems in interval spaces, J. Math. Anal. Appl. 189,297-309(1995).
- [3] G. Debreu, A social equilibrium existence theorem, Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci, U.S.A. 38, 886-895(1952).
- [4] X.P. Ding and K.K. Tan, On equilibria of non—compact generalized games, J. Math. Anal. Appl., 177,226-238(1993).
- [5] X.P. Ding, W.K. Kim and K.K. Tan, A section theorem and its applications, Bull. Austral. Math. Soc. 46, 205-212(1992).
- [6] A.K. Dubey, A. Narayan and R.P. Dubey, Maximal elements and pair of generalized games in locally convex topological vector spaces, Int. J. of Math. Sci. & Engg. Appls, 5 No. III, 371-380 (May, 2011).
- [7] A.K. Dubey, A. Narayan and R.P. Dubey, Fixed Points, Maximal elements and equilibria of generalized games, Int. J. of Pure and Appl. Math., 75(4), 413-425(2012).
- [8] A.K. Dubey and A. Narayan, Maximal elements and pair of generalized games for U-majorized and condensing correspondences, Nonlinear Fuct. Anal. & Appl. Vol.18, No. 2,259-267(2013).
- [9] K. Fan, Fixed-point and minimax theorems in locally convex topological linear spaces, Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci. U.S.A. 38,121-126(1952).
- [10] C.J. Himmelberg, Fixed points of compact multifunctions, J. Math. Anal. Appl. 38,205-207(1972).
- [11] N. Huang, Some new equilibrium theorems for abstract economies, Appl. Math. Lett., Vol.11, No.1, 41-45(1998).
- [12] D.I. Rim and W.K. Kim, A fixed point theorem and existence of equilibrium for abstract economies, Bull. Austral. Math. Soc. 45, 385-394(1992).
- [13] W. Shafer and H. Sonnenschein, Equilibrium in abstract economies without order preferences, J. Math. Econom., 2, 345-348 (1975).
- [14] K.K.Tan and J. Yu, A new minimax inequalities with applications to existence theorems of equilibrium points, J. Optim. Theory Appl. 82, 105-120 (1994).
- [15] K.K. Tan and X.Z.Yuan, Approximation method and equilibria of abstract economies, Proc. Amer. Math. Soc. 122, 503-510 (1994).
- [16] E. Tarafdar, An extension of Fan's Fixed point theorem and equilibrium point of abstract economy, Comment. Math. Univ. Carolin. 31,723-730(1990).

- [17] E. Tarafdar and X.Z. Yuan, Equilibria for non–compact generalized games, Bull. Polish Acad. Sci. Math. 41, 229-239(1993).
- [18] X.Wu, A new fixed point theorem and its applications Proc., Amer. Math. Soc., Vol.125,no.6, 1779-1783(1997).
- [19] N.C. Yannelis, Equilibria in non–cooperative models of competition, J. Econom. Theory 41, 96-111(1987).
- [20] N.C.Yannelis, N.D. Prabhakar, Existence of maximal elements and equilibria in linear topological spaces, J. Math. Econom.,12, 233-245(1983).